

Electrical Conductances for Tetraalkylammonium Bromides, LiBF₄ and LiAsF₆ in Tetrahydrofuran at 25°

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Electrical conductance data have been reported for tetraalkylammonium bromides, R₄NBr (R = butyl to heptyl), lithium tetrafluoroborate (LiBF₄) and lithium hexafluoroarsenate (LiAsF₆) in tetrahydrofuran (THF) at 25°. Analysis of data by the Fuoss-Kraus theory of conductance reveals the presence of both ion-pairs and triple ions. The ion-pair (*K_P*) and triple-ion (*K_T*) formation constants of these salts in tetrahydrofuran (THF) have been compared with the values obtained in 1,2-dimethoxyethane (1,2-DME). The comparison shows that the lower homologues of the studied R₄NBr salts are more associated in THF than in 1,2-DME whereas the *K_T* values in majority cases are much higher in 1,2-DME than in THF with the exception of LiAsF₆. The results have been explained with the help of configurational entropy and molecular model theory.

Progress in battery technology using the lithium electrolytes in etheral solutions¹ has occurred largely in the last decade. Recently, there has been a renewed interest², after the classical work of Fuoss and Kraus³ in the thirties, in the study of association and dimerisation of electrolytes in media of low permittivity. This has been particularly so important because knowledge of the state of association of the electrolytes and the type and the structure of the complex species in solution is essential for the optimal choice of solvents and electrolytes. Previously, Sellers *et al.*⁴ interpreted the conductance behaviour of weak acids and bases in non-aqueous solvents in terms of complex equilibria. Hojo *et al.*⁵ investigated the formation of triple ions for substituted ammonium halides in acetonitrile from conductivity and voltammetric data. The molecular relaxation dynamics and structure of lithium salts have been studied by Petrucci *et al.*^{2,6-10} from ultrasonic absorption and electrical conductivity measurements in media of low permittivity. The conductivity of tetraalkylammonium salts in polyaromatic solvents has also been studied recently by Abbot and Schiffrin¹¹ who showed the formation of triple ions by fitting the Fuoss-Kraus equation to the conductance data.

Recently, we have reported the formation of triple ions of tetraalkylammonium bromides in 1,2-dimethoxyethane ($\epsilon = 7.01$) from conductivity measurements¹². The study has been extended to tetrahydrofuran, a solvent having similar physical characteristics like 1,2-dimethoxyethane and the result is discussed herein.

Results and Discussion

The equivalent conductance (Λ) vs the concentration (*c*) data of the electrolytes in THF at 25° are recorded in Table 1. Fig. 1 presents the plots of Λ vs *c* for tetrabutyl-, tetrapentyl-, tetrahexyl-, tetraheptyl-bromides (lower homologues are insoluble in THF), LiBF₄ and LiAsF₆ at 25°. A minimum is clearly visible in every case.

The conductance data have been analysed by the Fuoss-Kraus triple-ion theory¹³ in the form as given below,

$$\Lambda g(c)^{1/2} = \frac{\Lambda_o}{K_p^{1/2}} + \frac{\Lambda_o^T K_T}{K_p^{1/2}} \left(1 - \frac{\Lambda}{\Lambda_o} \right) c \quad (1)$$

$$g(c) = \frac{\exp \left(- \frac{\beta'}{\Lambda_o^{1/2}} (c\Lambda)^{1/2} \right)}{\left(1 - \frac{S}{\Lambda_o^{3/2}} (c\Lambda)^{1/2} \right) \left(1 - \frac{\Lambda}{\Lambda_o} \right)^{1/2}} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 1. Plots of log Λ vs log c for Bu₄NBr, Pent₄NBr, Hex₄NBr, Hept₄NBr, LiBF₄ and LiAsF₆ in THF at 25°.

$$\beta' = \frac{1.8247 \times 10^6}{(\epsilon T)^{3/2}} \quad (3)$$

$$S = \alpha \Lambda_0 + \beta = \frac{0.8206 \times 10^6}{(\epsilon T)^{3/2}} \Lambda_0 + \frac{82.501}{\eta \alpha (\epsilon T)^{1/2}} \quad (4)$$

In the above equation β' is the Debye-Hückel activity coefficient, S the limiting Onsager coefficient and

the other terms have their usual significance. Also, Λ₀ is the sum of the equivalent conductances of the simple ions at infinite dilution and Λ₀^T the sum of the values for the two kinds of triple-ions: R₄N(Br₂)⁻ and (R₄N)₂⁺Br for R₄NBr salts, Li(BF₄)₂⁻ and Li₂(BF₄)⁺ for LiBF₄ and Li(AsF₆)₂⁻ and Li₂(AsF₆)⁺ for LiAsF₆; K_p and

TABLE 1 - ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY OF ELECTROLYTES IN TETRAHYDRO-FURAN AT 25^o

10 ⁻⁴ C mol dm ⁻³	Λ S cm ² mol ⁻¹	10 ⁻⁴ C mol dm ⁻³	Λ S cm ² mol ⁻¹	10 ⁻⁴ C mol dm ⁻³	Λ S cm ² mol ⁻¹
Bu ₄ NBr		Pent ₄ NBr		Hex ₄ NBr	
2.969	4.23	4.879	3.01	6.032	2.53
4.690	3.12	6.524	2.62	8.565	2.07
5.850	2.70	8.059	2.32	9.983	1.89
7.239	2.35	9.006	2.21	10.690	1.82
9.050	2.12	10.958	1.95	12.698	1.66
10.550	1.94	22.500	1.44	15.983	1.49
14.896	1.71	35.765	1.26	21.852	1.31
21.550	1.53	43.892	1.23	30.918	1.18
35.242	1.44	55.898	1.21	39.894	1.12
58.126	1.40	68.498	1.20	46.598	1.08
74.126	1.40	84.958	1.20	56.894	1.06
91.215	1.40	93.958	1.20	63.698	1.05
103.514	1.40	100.151	1.21	71.455	1.05
149.173	1.42	109.895	1.22	84.134	1.05
209.185	1.46	129.454	1.23	109.842	1.08
298.473	1.50	145.699	1.25	126.492	1.09
365.298	1.55	167.894	1.26	155.131	1.12
420.589	1.56	175.623	1.27	169.482	1.14
623.970	1.65	189.857	1.28	183.586	1.15
		221.589	1.32	208.934	1.19
		289.492	1.39	230.418	1.21
		314.596	1.40	241.253	1.22
		612.558	1.64	292.956	1.27
				351.611	1.33
Hept ₄ NBr		LiBF ₄		LiAsF ₆	
8.494	2.26	9.489	1.42	7.698	16.51
9.010	2.19	15.987	1.06	9.279	15.55
9.895	2.04	29.829	0.79	15.895	12.92
10.957	1.95	37.985	0.71	43.897	9.48
13.985	1.73	48.580	0.64	74.875	8.27
15.315	1.65	53.500	0.62	90.768	8.00
17.987	1.55	74.598	0.55	109.764	7.68
20.285	1.46	90.386	0.51	132.983	7.45
25.316	1.27	118.765	0.47	148.925	7.35
29.849	1.23	223.943	0.41	169.021	7.39
36.983	1.17	272.149	0.40	180.943	7.27
43.895	1.13	307.826	0.40	213.792	7.27
66.986	1.08	382.967	0.40	224.976	7.26
80.689	1.07	439.467	0.40	309.267	7.53
94.986	1.07	576.928	0.42	378.769	7.79
120.289	1.08	615.938	0.43	484.693	8.02
139.468	1.09	871.613	0.47		
156.489	1.10	938.538	0.48		
189.542	1.14	1098.562	0.52		
268.498	1.22	1165.823	0.53		
319.286	1.26	1214.960	0.54		
356.894	1.30	1289.710	0.57		

K_T are the ion-pair and triple-ion formation constants respectively. The symmetrical approximation of the two possible formation constant of triple-ions equal

to each other has been considered⁷.

Neglecting, Λ/Λ₀, (S/Λ₀^{3/2})(cΛ)^{1/2} and assuming f_± = 1, lead to g(c) = 1 in equation (1) and we get,

$$\Lambda(c)^{1/2} = \frac{\Lambda_0}{K_p^{1/2}} + \frac{\Lambda_0^T K_T}{K_p^{1/2}} c \quad (5)$$

For the present data, it was found that equation (5) was inadequate, the data showing a downward curvature when plotted as Λ(c)^{1/2} vs c. On the contrary, equation (1) gives reasonably straight line (a representative plot for Hept₄NBr is shown in Fig. 2). For evaluation of K_p and K_T values from

Fig. 2. Representative plot of Λg(c)c^{1/2} vs c (1 - Λ/Λ₀) for Hept₄NBr in THF at 25^o.

equation (1), the average Λ₀η₀ values of R₄NBr salts at 25^o were taken from the work of Krumgalz¹⁴. Λ₀η₀-value for LiBF₄ and LiAsF₆ in 1,2-DME at 25^o was taken from literature^{2,7}. Therefore, from Walden's rule the Λ₀-values of all the salts in THF at 25^o have been calculated and presented in Table 2. Linear regression analysis of equation (1) gives correlation coefficient (r²), intercept and slope and the values have been reported in Table 2. In solving equation (1), Λ₀^T, the triple-ion conductance, was set equal to 2/3Λ₀⁵. This has been specially done so for relative comparison of K_T values for the same electrolytes in different solvents¹⁶. The K_p and K_T values thus evaluated are recored in Table 3. It is clear from Table 3 that major

TABLE 2 - VALUES OF COEFFICIENTS FROM REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Salt	S	Λ° cm ² mol ⁻¹	r^2	Intercept	Slope
Bu ₄ NBr	123.33	0.9835	6.85×10^{-2} (± 0.0003)	5.281 (± 0.008)	
Pent ₄ NBr	118.33	0.9952	6.21×10^{-2} (± 0.0002)	5.200 (± 0.005)	
Hex ₄ NBr	114.63	0.9972	5.12×10^{-2} (± 0.0001)	5.166 (± 0.002)	
Hept ₄ NBr	112.24	0.9968	5.54×10^{-2} (± 0.0001)	4.813 (± 0.002)	
LiBF ₄	122.61	0.9944	3.65×10^{-2} (± 0.0019)	1.079 (± 0.002)	
LiAsF ₆	132.80	0.9960	45.65×10^{-2} (± 0.0001)	25.961 (± 0.105)	

portion of the electrolytes exist as ion-pairs with only a minor proportion as triple-ions. Using the values of K_p from Table 3, the interionic distance parameter q_B has been calculated with the help of the Bjerrum's theory of ionic association¹⁷ which can be written as

$$K_p = \frac{4 \pi N_A}{1000} \left(\frac{|Z_1 Z_2| e^2}{\epsilon k T} \right)^3 Q(b) \quad (6)$$

TABLE 3 - ION-PAIR AND TRIPLE-ION FORMATION CONSTANTS IN THF AT 25°

Salt	$10^{-6} K_p$ (mol dm ⁻³) ⁻¹	K_T (mol dm ⁻³) ⁻¹
Bu ₄ NBr	3.24	115.68
Pent ₄ NBr	6.63	125.61
Hex ₄ NBr	5.02	151.47
Hept ₄ NBr	4.11	130.42
LiBF ₄	11.30	44.36
LiAsF ₆	0.08	85.30

where $Q(b) = \int_2^b y^{-4} \exp y \, dy$

and $b = \frac{|Z_1 Z_2| e^2}{q_B \epsilon k T}$

The q_B values obtained by the above procedure are recorded in Table 4. The $Q(b)$ values have been taken from literature¹⁸. Table 4 reveals that q_B is almost similar for all the tetraalkylammonium salts whereas the actual ionic size changes by 0.94 Å. This may be accounted by assuming that the Br⁻ ion can easily penetrate to some extent into the void spaces between the alkyl chains, as suggested

by Abbott and Schiffrin¹¹ in other systems. Thus increase in chain-length in case of tetraalkylammonium ions does not greatly affect the distance of closest approach between the two ions. However, we see that an increase in the chain-length increases the ion-pair association constant to some extent. The q_B values calculated from equation (6) are much less in comparison with the r_c values (sum of the crystallographic radii) as reported in the literature¹⁹, suggesting that contact ion-pairs for tetraalkylammonium bromides probably exist in solution. This may cause a decrease in the degree of freedom of the cation in the ion-pair, which results in the loss of configurational entropy for the contact pair. Generally, K_p values do not change significantly for quarternary ammonium ions with chain-lengths greater than C₃. The small changes in the K_p values as observed in Table 3 may thus be related to entropic contributions as discussed above. Table 3 also shows that K_p value of LiBF₄ is much higher than that of LiAsF₆. Also from the q_B values reported in Table 4 we see that the minimum distance between ions in ion-pairs for these two electrolytes is much higher than the size of the average ionic diameter as reported in the literature^{11,16}. This indicates that in case of LiBF₄ and LiAsF₆ perhaps some solvent molecules have been included in the first coordination shell of the central ion. Further, a decrease in dielectric constant generally causes an increase in the association constant of the free ions. In case of LiBF₄, BF₄⁻ ion probably experiences a lower dielectric constant resulting in a lower interionic distance value than that of LiAsF₆ (the ratio q_B/r_c is 1.29 and 1.44 for LiBF₄ and LiAsF₆ respectively) and this is most likely the effect which is being observed here.

TABLE 4 - THE q_B , a_T AND r_c VALUES FOR THE SALTS IN THF AT 25°

Salt	$q_B/10^8$ cm	$a_T/10^8$ cm	$r_c/10^8$ cm
Bu ₄ NBr	4.06	4.50	6.74 ^a
Pent ₄ NBr	4.03	4.37	7.09 ^a
Hex ₄ NBr	3.96	3.70	7.40 ^a
Hept ₄ NBr	4.01	4.29	7.68 ^a
LiBF ₄	3.80	-	2.95 ^a
LiAsF ₆	5.61	4.80	3.90 ^b
^a Ref. 19.		^b Ref. 16.	

The interionic distance (a_T) for a triple ion has also been calculated for these electrolytes according to the original theory of Fuoss and Kraus³ as given by the expressions,

$$K_T = \frac{2 \pi N_A a_T^3}{1000} I(b_3) \quad (7)$$

$$\text{where } I(b_3) = \frac{e^2}{a_T \epsilon k T}$$

$I(b_3)$ is a double integral which has been tabulated in the literature¹⁸ for a wide range of values of b_3 . Since the term $I(b_3)$ is also a function of a_T , so a_T values were calculated by an iterative procedure with the help of equation (7) and given in Table 4. The table shows that a_T values of the electrolytes are greater than the corresponding q_B values but the values are much less than the expected theoretical result, $a_T = 1.5 q_B$. This may be due to repulsive forces between the two anions or two cations in the case of the triple-ions MA_2 or M_2A respectively.

It is interesting to compare the values of K_P and K_T (Table 5) with the corresponding data for these electrolytes in 1,2-DME ($\epsilon = 7.01$, $\eta_0 = 0.0041$ P). The comparison shows that the electrolytes Bu₄NBr and Pent₄NBr are more associated in THF than in 1,2-DME. In case of LiAsF₆, the value of K_P is very close to each other in these two solvent media. The triple-ion formation constants (K_T) of these electrolytes in 1,2-DME are much higher than that in THF with the exception of LiAsF₆, where reverse trend has been observed. The observed difference in K_P and K_T values can

be explained by molecular scale model². It is likely that chelation of R₄N⁺ and Li⁺ by 1,2-DME shifts equilibrium (8) toward the left, thus decreasing K_P .

On the other hand, the steric hindrance caused by the -CH₂- group adjacent to the etheral group of the THF may cause solvation hindrance which favours the anion as a competitor for the first coordination shell around M⁺. This may shift equilibrium (8) toward the right, increasing K_P .

The ion-pair and triple-ion concentrations (C_P and C_T respectively) of the electrolytes are reported in Table 5 at the highest concentrations for individual ions as tabulated in Table 1 using the relations,

$$C_P = c (1 - \alpha - 3 \alpha_T) \quad (9)$$

$$\alpha = (K_P^{1/2} c^{1/2})^{-1} \quad (10)$$

$$\alpha_T = (K_T / K_P^{1/2}) c^{1/2} \quad (11)$$

$$C_T = (K_T / K_P^{1/2}) c^{3/2} \quad (12)$$

The results indicate that the ions are mainly present as ion-pairs even at such high concentrations with a small fraction as triple-ions.

Experimental

Tetrahydrofuran (THF) was kept for several days over KOH, then refluxed for 24 h and distilled over LiAlH₄. The b.p. (66°), density (0.8807 g

TABLE 5 — COMPARISON OF K_P AND K_T VALUES IN THF AND 1,2-DME AT 25°

Salt	C*		10 ⁴ C _P		10 ⁴ C _T		10 ⁻⁶ K _P		K _T	
	THF	DME	THF	DME	THF	DME	THF	DME	THF	DME
Bu ₄ NBr	0.062	0.03 ^a	588.85	271.90	9.92	8.99	3.24	2.39	115.68	267.58
Pent ₄ NBr	0.061	0.03 ^a	578.91	270.11	9.93	9.43	3.63	1.12	125.61	192.01
Hex ₄ NBr	0.035	0.03 ^a	335.88	281.39	4.43	5.95	5.02	5.18	151.47	260.64
Hept ₄ NBr	0.035	0.03 ^a	336.44	282.69	4.21	5.51	4.11	4.74	130.42	230.74
LiBF ₄	0.129	0.10 ^b	1270.50	4.55	6.11	4.56	11.30	12.00	44.36	50
LiAsF ₆	0.048	0.20 ^c	379.96	0.30	3.08	0.03	0.08	0.10	85.30	28

*Maximum concentrations at which calculations have been made..

^aRef. 12. ^bRef. 7. ^cRef. 16.

cm^{-3}) and viscosity ($\eta_0 = 0.0046 \text{ P}$) compared well with the literature values⁸. The specific conductance of THF was ca. $0.81 \times 10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 25° . Tetraalkylammonium bromides (Fluka) were purified as described earlier¹². LiBF_4 and LiAsF_6 (Fluka, Puriss) were redried under reduced pressure at 60° for 36 h.

Conductance measurements were made by a Pye-Unicam PW 9509 conductivity meter at a frequency of 2000 Hz using a dip-type cell of cell constant 0.747 cm^{-1} and having an accuracy of $\pm 0.1\%$. The measurements were made in an oil-bath maintained at $25 \pm 0.005^\circ$. The details of experimental procedure have been described earlier²⁰. Solutions for conductance work were prepared by weight. The stock solution was kept in desiccator and used within 6–8 h. The conversion of molality into molarity was done using the density values.

Density and viscosity of solvent and solutions were measured in an Ostwald-Sprengel type pycnometer and suspended level Ubbelohde-type viscometer at $25 \pm 0.01^\circ$ with an accuracy of $\pm 3 \times 10^{-5} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ and 0.05% respectively. The dielectric constant of THF ($\epsilon = 7.58$) was taken from the literature¹⁹.

References

1. J. L. GOLDMAN, R. M. MARK, J. H. YOUNG and V. R. KOCH, *J. Electrochim. Soc.*, 1980, **127**, 1461.
2. Y. HARADA, M. SALAMON and S. PETRUCCI, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1985, **89**, 2005.
3. R. M. FUOSS and C. A. KRAUS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **55**, 2387.
4. N. G. SELLERS, P. M. P. ELLER and J. A. CARUSO, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1972, **76**, 3618.
5. M. HOJO, T. TAKIGUCHI, M. HAGIWARA, H. NAGAI and Y. IMAI, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1989, **93**, 955.
6. S. ONISHI, H. FARBER and S. PETRUCCI, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1980, **84**, 2922.
7. H. MASER, M. DELSIGNORE, M. NEWSTEIN and S. PETRUCCI, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1984, **88**, 5100.
8. P. JAGODZINSKI and S. PETRUCCI, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1974, **78**, 917.
9. M. DELSIGNORE, H. FERBER and S. PETRUCCI, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1986, **90**, 66.
10. D. SAAR and S. PETRUCCI, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1986, **90**, 3326.
11. A. P. ABBOTT and D. J. SCHIFFRIN, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1990, **86**, 1453.
12. D. NANDI, S. DAS and D. K. HAZRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, **27**, 574.
13. R. M. FUOSS and F. ACCASCINA, "Electrolytic Conductance, Interscience, New York, 1959.
14. B. S. KRUMGALZ, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1983, **79**, 571.
15. S. BOILESU and P. EMERGY, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1976, **21**, 647.
16. H. FARBER, D. E. IRISH and S. PETRUCCI, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1983, **87**, 3515.
17. N. BJERRUM, *Kgl. Danske Videnskab. Selskab.*, 1926, **9**, 7.
18. H. S. HARNED and B. B. OWEN, "Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Solutions", 3rd, ed., Reinhold, New York, 1958.
19. "Physical Chemistry of Organic Solvent systems", eds. A. K. COVINGTON and T. DICKENSON, Plenum, New York, 1973, pp. 5, 261.
20. D. DASGUPTA, S. DAS and D. K. HAZRA, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1988, **84**, 1057.